

Master's Thesis:

Optimizing Process Mining Visualizations

Appendix A - Study Materials

Hauer, Franz Gerhard

Date of Birth: 28.02.1999

Student ID: 11913683

Supervisor: Univ.Prof. Dr. Sarah Spiekermann-Hoff

Co-Supervisor: Djordje Djurica, Ph.D.

Vienna University of Economics and Business

21.12.2025

Table of contents

1. Overview of the Experiment.....	3
2. Participants Recruiting	4
3. Survey Flow	5
4. Process Visualizations	13
5. Tasks.....	21
6. Scoring Sheet	22

1. Overview of the Experiment

This experiment was conducted as part of a master's thesis by Franz Hauer at the Vienna University of Economics and Business, supervised by Djordje Djurica.

The Study investigates how different structural elements and design decisions in process model visualizations influence the ability of users to understand and analyze business processes. It aims to advance the understanding of how these design decisions impact comprehension, accuracy and efficiency in process analysis tasks.

This experiment focuses on time-based process visualizations. It evaluates the performance of the timeline-based DFG (short Timeline DFG) compared to other traditional visualizations like the Performance DFG and the Dotted Chart.

The tasks include structure / control-flow related tasks like identifying the start and end activities as well as time-related tasks such as identifying the shortest or longest waiting time.

The data used in this study comes from the BPI Challenge 2013 that captures real-world event logs provided by Volvo IT Belgium. The event log includes process instances from an incident management system, that supports the organization's IT service management activities. The incident management process aims to restore the normal service operation as fast as possible when incidents occur to ensure the highest possible level of service quality and availability.

For conducting the study we used Qualtrics, for recruitment of the participants we used Prolific.

This document includes an overview of the survey flow and contains the materials and tasks used for the experiment. However, to get the full picture of the experiment, please read the thesis.

2. Participants Recruiting

Participants were recruited using Prolific (<https://www.prolific.com/>)

Pre Screening of Participants

The following pre-screening configurations were made.

Prescreen participants

Find the right participants for your study using our 300+ screeners. Can't find the screener you're looking for? Use [Custom screening](#) in your study.

Fluent languages English	View
Highest education level completed Technical/community college, Undergraduate degree (BA/BSc/other), Graduate degree (MA/MSc/MPhil/other), Doctorate degree (PhD/other)	View
Approval Rate 90-100	View
Technology use at work 4 or 6 times a week, about once a day, more than once a day	View
Work Function Data Analysis, Finance or Accounting, IT / Information Networking / Information Security, Operations	View

3. Survey Flow

1. General instructions, information and consent

Welcome

Dear participant,
welcome to this study!

This study investigates how different structural elements and design decisions in process model visualizations influence the ability of users to understand and analyze business processes. Your participation helps us to advance our understanding of how these design decisions impact comprehension, accuracy and efficiency in process analysis tasks.

The study is conducted as part of a master's thesis by Franz Hauer at the Vienna University of Economics and Business, supervised by Djordje Djurica. We sincerely appreciate your contribution and the time and effort you dedicate to participate in our experiment.

The study consists of four sections. First, you will receive an introduction to a process model based on a specific visualization design. Then, you will assess **two process graphs**, each accompanied by **nine tasks** related to interpreting and understanding of the process. Finally, a short questionnaire will collect demographic information and information about your prior knowledge. The expected duration of the study is **30 minutes**.

The data used in this study comes from the BPI Challenge 2013 that captures real-world event logs provided by Volvo IT Belgium. The event log includes process instances from an incident management system, that supports the organization's IT service management activities. The incident management process aims to restore the normal service operation as fast as possible when incidents occur to ensure the highest possible level of service quality and availability.

Confidentiality

The names of individuals or organizations are not required in any of the responses. You will not be asked to disclose confidential or sensitive information about yourself or the organization you may be affiliated with. All responses will be stored without reference to the names of individual persons.

There are no risks (in excess of the risks of everyday office work) associated with your participation in this study.
In case you have more questions about the experiment, you can contact us by sending an email to franz.hauer@s.wu.ac.at

To improve the quality of the answers, we kindly ask you to mute your phone and remove any other distractions during the study.

You are now ready to begin the study. Let's get started!

2. Graph specific instructions:

Every participant is assigned to one of five experimental groups, each group having an own process visualization. The participant receives an introduction for the process visualization he/she was assigned to. In the following you can find the instructions for each process visualization.

Timeline DFG with vertical spacing

G2_intro

Instructions - Let's get familiar with the process model!

Process Discovery is a process mining practice that aims to create process models from event logs to visualize the actual behaviour of business processes in practice. One of the most widely used and simplest representations for discovered process models is the Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) which represents activities as nodes and shows arrows between them when one activity directly follows another in a recorded process instance.

A Timeline DFG is an extension of this approach that adds a time axis to the process model. It has the following structure:

- A timeline is displayed as a vertical axis on the left side of the DFG.
- Activities are vertically aligned based on the average time of their occurrence relative to the start of the process.
- Each node (circle) on the timeline shows the average point in time at which the corresponding activity occurs.
- The vertical distance between activities reflects the average waiting time between them. A semi-logarithmic scale is used.
- The black circles at the top and bottom of the process graph represent the start and end nodes that are not considered as activities.
- In the process graph, the rectangles represent distinct activities.
- The directed arcs in the DFG connect these activities to show the directly-follows relationships.
- Each arc is annotated with the frequency of how often one activity follows another across all process instances.

Timeline DFG without vertical spacing

G1_intro

Instructions - Let's get familiar with the process model!

Process Discovery is a process mining practice that aims to create process models from event logs to visualize the actual behaviour of business processes in practice. One of the most widely used and simplest representations for discovered process models is the Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) which represents activities as nodes and shows arrows between them when one activity directly follows another in a recorded process instance.

A Timeline DFG is an extension of this approach that adds a time axis to the process model. It has the following structure:

- A timeline is displayed as a vertical axis on the left side of the DFG.
- Activities are vertically aligned based on the average time of their occurrence relative to the start of the process.
- Each node (circle) on the timeline shows the average point in time at which the corresponding activity occurs.
- The vertical arrows between time nodes reflect the average waiting time between the activities.
- The black circles at the top and bottom of the process graph represent the start and end nodes that are not considered as activities.
- In the process graph, the rectangles represent distinct activities.
- The directed arcs in the DFG connect these activities to show the directly-follows relationships.
- Each arc is annotated with the frequency of how often one activity follows another across all process instances.

Timeline DFG with folding

G3_Intro

Instructions - Let's get familiar with the process model!

Process Discovery is a process mining practice that aims to create process models from event logs to visualize the actual behaviour of business processes in practice. One of the most widely used and simplest representations for discovered process models is the Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) which represents activities as nodes and shows arrows between them when one activity directly follows another in a recorded case.

A Timeline DFG is an extension of this approach that adds a time axis to the process model. It has the following structure:

- A timeline is displayed as a vertical axis on the left side of the DFG.
- Activities are vertically aligned based on the average time of their occurrence relative to the start of the process.
- Each node (circle) on the timeline shows the average point in time at which the corresponding activity occurs.
- The vertical arrows between time nodes reflect the average waiting time between the activities.
- In the process graph, the nodes (rectangles) represent distinct activities.
- The directed arcs in the DFG connect these nodes to show the directly-follows relationships.
- Each arc is annotated with the frequency of how often one activity follows another across all process instances.

Performance DFG

G4_Intro

Instructions - Let's get familiar with the process model!

Process Discovery is a process mining practice that aims to create process models from event logs to visualize the actual behaviour of business processes in practice. One of the most widely used and simplest representations for discovered process models is the Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) which represents activities as nodes and shows arrows between them when one activity directly follows another in a recorded case. It has the following structure:

- Nodes (rectangles) represent distinct activities of the process
- Directed arcs connect these nodes to show the directly-follows relationships
- The black circles at the top and bottom of the process graph represent the start and end nodes that are not considered as activities.
- Each arc is annotated with an average time duration that indicates the delay between two related activities across all cases.

Dotted Chart

G5_Intro

Instructions - Let's get familiar with the process model!

Process Discovery is a process mining practice that aims to create process models from event logs to visualize the actual behaviour of business processes in practice. A Dotted Chart is a visualization that focuses on displaying the distribution of events across cases over time. It has the following structure:

- Each horizontal row represents a single case
- Each dot represents an activity within a case. These dots are colour coded to indicate the different activities
- The x-axis shows the time when an activity occurred, measured relative to the start of the case
- The y-axis displays the individual cases
- The distance between dots on the x-axis shows the time gap between activities within a case

Dotted Chart (Time in Days)

3. Graph specific Tasks

Participants receive 9 tasks for each level of complexity (low and high process model complexity). We applied counterbalancing which means that half of the people receive the high complex model first, while the others receive the low complex first. (see tasks section)

4. Demographics

Demographic Questions:

Demographic Survey

As a final step, we kindly ask you to complete a brief demographic survey.

What is your gender?

Male

Female

Non-binary / third gender

Prefer not to say

What is the highest level of school you have completed or the highest degree you have received?

Less than a high-school degree

High school degree or equivalent

Bachelors degree

Master degree

PhD Degree

Other (please specify)

What is your current employment status?

Employed full-time

Employed part-time

Unemployed

Pokemon Coach

Student

Retired

Self-employed

Unable to work

What is your country of residence? (Leave empty in case you do not want to respond)

Work Experience

Do you have any work experience as a process analyst or equivalent?

Yes

No

Do you have any experience working with process models?

Yes

No

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, how many years of experience do you have?

Please select 'Agree' for this statement to show you are paying attention

Disagree

Agree

Other

Domain Knowledge

Rate the extent of your experience regarding the following domains

	Not familiar at all	Slightly familiar	Moderately familiar	Very familiar	Extremely familiar
Incident Management System Process	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments & Suggestions

Please insert any comments that can help us improve our research.

You answered to all the questions in this survey. Thank you! Please, move to the next page to finalize your participation.

4. Process Visualizations

Timeline DFG with vertical spacing

Figure 1: Timeline DFG with spacing - low complexity

Timeline DFG without vertical spacing

Figure 3: Timeline DFG without spacing - low complexity

Figure 4: Timeline DFG without spacing - high complexity

Timeline DFG with folding mechanism applied

Figure 5: Timeline DFG with folding - low complexity

Figure 6: Timeline DFG with folding - high complexity

Performance DFG

Figure 7: Performance DFG - low complexity

Dotted Chart

Figure 9: Dotted Chart - low complexity

Figure 10: Dotted Chart - high complexity

5. Tasks

Task	Question	Type	Category
1	Which activities start the process? Choose the starting activities.	Multiple choice	Control flow / structure
2	Which activities end the process? Choose the end activities.	Multiple choice	Control flow / structure
3	Which activities follow directly after “Accepted–In Progress”? Select all activities that immediately follow this activity. Do not consider self-loops.	Multiple choice	Control flow / structure
4	How many distinct paths exist from start to end? Do not consider loops or self-loops.	Open numeric input	Control flow / structure
5	What is the longest waiting time between two sequential activities? Select the last activity of the two. Don't consider self-loops and the start/end nodes as activities.	Single choice	Time-related
6	What is the shortest waiting time between two sequential activities? Select the last activity of the two. Don't consider self-loops and the start/end nodes as activities.	Single choice	Time-related
7	Which path has the shortest duration from start to end? Rank all activities following that path from start to end in correct order via drag and drop.	Ranking	Time-related
8	How long does the shortest path you identified take? Enter as number + unit (m = minutes, h = hours, d = days), e.g. 30m, 2h, 2d	Open numeric input	Time-related
9	Which activities can be repeated according to the DFG? Select all activities that are performed more than once in the same process instance.	Multiple choice	Control-flow / structure

6. Scoring Sheet

Task	CorrectAnswer1	CorrectAnswer2	CorrectAnswer3	CorrectAnswer4	CorrectAnswer5	CorrectAnswer6	CorrectAnswer7	CorrectAnswer8	CorrectAnswer	Number of Correct answers
01.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
01.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed								2
01.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved						4
01.T4	Completed-Closed	6								1
01.T5	Completed-In Call									1
01.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call									1
01.T7	48m	47m								1
01.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								1
01.c.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
01.c.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed	Completed-Resolved							3
01.c.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
01.c.T4	Completed-Closed	20	40							1
01.c.T5	Accepted-Wait - User									1
01.c.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call									1
01.c.T7	5h	4h	6h							1
01.c.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-In Progress	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
02.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
02.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed								2
02.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved						4
02.T4	Completed-Closed	6								1
02.T5	Completed-In Call									1
02.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call									1
02.T7	48m	47m	47mins							3
02.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								1
02.c.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
02.c.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed	Completed-Resolved							3
02.c.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
02.c.T4	Completed-Closed	20	40							1
02.c.T5	Accepted-Wait - User									1
02.c.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call	Queued-Awaiting Assignment,Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call								1
02.c.T7	5h	4h	6h							1
02.c.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-In Progress	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
03.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
03.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed								2
03.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved						4
03.T4	Completed-Resolved	6								1
03.T5	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Closed								1
03.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call	Queued-Awaiting Assignment,Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call								2
03.T7	48m	47m	48							3
03.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								1
03.c.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
03.c.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Resolved	Completed-Closed							3
03.c.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
03.c.T4	Completed-Closed	20	40							1
03.c.T5	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved								2
03.c.T6	Accepted-In Progress	Completed-Resolved	Completed-Closed	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait				6
03.c.T7	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call	Queued-Awaiting Assignment,Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call								2
03.c.T8	1d	1d	1							1
03.c.T9	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-In Progress	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
04.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
04.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed								2
04.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved						4
04.T4	Completed-Resolved	6								1
04.T5	Completed-In Call									1
04.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call									1
04.T7	45m	45 minutes								1
04.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								3
04.T9	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
04.c.T1	Completed-In Call	Completed-Resolved	Completed-Closed							3
04.c.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Resolved	Completed-Closed							3
04.c.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
04.c.T4	Completed-Resolved	20	40							1
04.c.T5	Accepted-In Progress									1
04.c.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call									1
04.c.T7	47m	47m	47 minutes							1
04.c.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-In Progress	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
05.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
05.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed								2
05.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved						4
05.T4	Completed-Closed	6								1
05.T5	Completed-In Call									1
05.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call	Queued-Awaiting Assignment,Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call								2
05.T7	48m	47m	48							3
05.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								1
05.c.T1	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Accepted-In Progress								2
05.c.T2	Completed-In Call	Completed-Closed	Completed-Resolved							3
05.c.T3	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Wait - Customer	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9
05.c.T4	Completed-Closed	20	40							1
05.c.T5	Accepted-Wait - User									1
05.c.T6	Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call	Queued-Awaiting Assignment,Accepted-In Progress,Completed-In Call								2
05.c.T7	5h	4h	6h							1
05.c.T8	Queued-Awaiting Assignment	Completed-In Call	Accepted-In Progress	Accepted-Wait - User	Completed-Resolved	Accepted-Wait - Vendor	Accepted-Assigned	Accepted-Wait - Implementation	Accepted-Wait	9

Figure 11: Scoring Sheet